

COATING EFFECTS OF COPPER IN CNT/CARBON FABRIC HYBRID COMPOSITES USING ELECTROPHORETIC DEPOSITION

O. Choi, S-B. Lee, J-H. Byun, W. Lee, J-W. Yi, B-S. Kim,
Composite Materials Research Group, Korea Institute of Materials Science
Changwon, 641-831, South Korea
bjh1673@kims.re.kr

Erik T. Thostenson, Tsu-Wei Chou
Center for Composite Materials and Department of Mechanical Engineering,
University of Delaware, 120 Spencer Lab., Newark, DE 19716, USA

SUMMARY

Electrophoretic process was applied to the deposition of carbon nanotubes on the surface of carbon fabrics in order to enhance the properties of CNT/carbon fabric hybrid composites. Carbon fabrics were modified by two methods: Cu deposition by cathodic method and Cu coating by thermal vaporization method. CNTs were modified by PEI and oxidation treatment. The effects of carbon fabric and CNTs modification were examined by comparing the electrical conductivity and the interlaminar shear strength of the composites. SEM images and EDS analysis confirmed that Cu and CNTs deposition on carbon fabrics was relatively dense and uniform. In the case of simultaneous deposition of Cu and CNTs on carbon fabrics, electrical conductivity in the thickness direction increased one order of magnitude, and interlaminar shear strength improved by 10%, compared with unmodified carbon fabric composites.

Keywords: Carbon nanotube, electrophoretic deposition, hybrid composite

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites have been successfully utilized in the structural parts, however, they have inherent weakness of delamination caused by the lack of through-thickness fibers. One possible measure to improve matrix dominant properties of laminated composites is to use carbon nanotube (CNT) reinforcements in the polymer matrices: *hybrid composites*. By addition of low content of CNTs, the mechanical and functional properties of polymers have shown significant improvement [1-3]. Given the excellent properties of CNTs, incorporation of them into composites has been pursued in many approaches: direct addition of CNTs into matrix using various dispersion methods, CNT growth on substrate reinforcement, CNT spraying, and so on. The ultimate goal of the hybrid composites is how to reinforce CNTs in micro composites system efficiently. In order to do this (1) CNT should be dispersed well in the system, (2) interfacial property between micro-nano reinforcement and matrix should be controlled, and (3) whole process should be simple and cost-effective.

Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) is one of the particular methods to fabricate multi-scale hybrid composites due to the high efficiency for the homogeneous deposition of charged particles on carbon fabrics [4-7]. By applying an electric field between electrodes, the particles in a suitable suspension move toward an anode or a cathode depending upon their electrical charges. When the particles are negatively charged, they move to an anodic substrate, which is called anodic process. The cathodic process means positively charged particles move toward a cathodic substrate. CNTs can be charged in negative or in positive using proper surface treatment in aqueous suspension. Oxidized CNTs using carboxylic functional group (COOH) can be negatively charged by losing hydrogen ions in distilled water. On the other hand polyethyleneimine (PEI) surfactant can have positive charge by getting hydrogen ion in aqueous suspension.

In this study, carbon fabrics as a substrate were coated with Cu for further improvement of electrical properties of composites, and the effect of Cu coating on the mechanical property have been examined. The effectiveness of anodic and cathodic processes has been evaluated with respect to the degree of electrophoretic deposition and the property enhancement of the hybrid composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The type of CNT is MWCNT, supplied by Hanwha Nanotech. Plain woven carbon fabrics (Mitsubishi TR50, 3k) were used as substrate materials. For a surfactant PEI (Aldrich, Mw. 25,000) was used. The nitric acid and the mixture of sulphuric/nitric acid were used for the oxidation of CNTs. As an opposite electrode to the carbon fabric a 0.3mm-thick Cu plate was used for the electrophoretic process. The resin for the composites fabrication was epoxy (YD128) with KBH 1089 as a curing agent (both from Kukdo Chemicals).

Sample Preparation

The table 1 summarizes the various modifications on carbon fabrics and CNTs. Type 1 is unmodified carbon fabrics without addition of CNTs as a control material. In order to evaluate the effect of Cu-modified carbon fabrics on the property of composites two types of samples without addition of CNTs were prepared: in Type 2, Cu was deposited on carbon fabrics by a cathodic process, and Type 4 has carbon fabrics coated with Cu by thermal evaporation method. Samples of Type 3 were prepared to examine the combined effects of Cu/CNTs deposition. In the case of Type 5 and 6 two kinds of acid solutions were used for the CNTs treatment.

Deposition/Coating of Cu on Carbon Fabrics (Type 2 and Type 4)

Cu deposition on carbon fabrics has been carried out by the electrophoretic process. When a Cu plate is connected to an anode and a carbon fabric is connected to a cathode, the ionized copper (Cu^{2+}) moves toward a carbon fabric and deposited on the surface. Another approach to provide higher conducting property to carbon fabrics was also

performed by coating of Cu using thermal evaporation method. Cu coating on the carbon fabric can intensify the attractive force of the substrate carbon fabric, expecting substantial deposition of CNTs on the substrate.

Table 1. Sample preparation by modification of carbon fabrics and CNTs

Type	Carbon Fabric Modification	CNT treatment	EPD type
1	Unmodified	Without CNTs	n/a
2	Cu deposited by EPD	Without CNTs	Cathodic
3	Cu deposited by EPD	PEI treated	Cathodic
4	Cu coated by thermal evaporation	Without CNTs	Anodic
5	Cu coated by thermal evaporation	H ₂ SO ₄ +HNO ₃ oxidized	Anodic
6	Cu coated by thermal evaporation	HNO ₃ oxidized	Anodic

CNT Deposition on Carbon Fabric: Cathodic Process (Type 3)

The colloidal suspension of PEI-treated 1.0wt% of CNTs and 0.5wt% of in distilled water medium was prepared for CNT deposition. A homogeneous dispersion of CNTs was carried out by a homo-mixer and ultrasonication. Carbon fabric of 80×80mm and 0.3mm-thick Cu plate were connected to a cathode and an anode of a power supply, respectively. These were placed in non-conducting plastic holder separated in 8mm distance.

CNT Deposition on Cu coated Carbon Fabric: Anodic Process (Type 5 and Type 6)

CNTs were modified by oxidation treatment using a nitric acid for the uniform dispersion and particle charging in the suspension. The mixture of the nitric acid and CNT was sonicated for 30min. Before being dried at 120°C for 24hrs, they were neutralized by rinsing with distilled water. Additional sonication has been carried out to disperse the CNTs in distilled water. To obtain further improvement in electrical conductivity, plain woven carbon fabrics were coated with copper via thermal evaporation method prior to EPD process. In the anodic process a Cu-coated carbon fabric and a copper plate were connected to an anode and a cathode of the power supply, respectively.

Composites Fabrication & Characterization

After electrophoresis processing, deposited carbon fabrics were dried in a 120°C oven for 24 hrs. For the fabrication of composite samples, twelve layers of the deposited fabric were laminated, and epoxy was injected by the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. Short beam shear tests based on ASTM 2344 were carried out to measure the interlaminar shear strength of the composite. The fractured surfaces were also observed by SEM. Both in-plane and out-of-plane electrical conductivities were measured for 15×15×3mm³ specimens using a Keithley 2100 multimeter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scanning Electron Microscope Observation

Figure 1 shows the SEM images of unmodified and Cu/CNT modified carbon fabric surfaces. Figure 1(a) of Type 1 shows unmodified carbon fabrics without any particle depositions. Copper deposition on the carbon fabric without CNT addition is shown in Figure 1(b). Carbon fabrics deposited with PEI-treated CNTs (simultaneous deposition of Cu and CNTs) is shown in Figure 1(c). Figure 1(d) shows the Cu-coated carbon fabric without addition of CNTs. Cu coated carbon fabrics deposited with acid-modified CNTs using $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4+\text{HNO}_3$ and HNO_3 are shown in Figure 1(e) and (f), respectively.

Comparing with unmodified carbon fabrics (Figure 1(a)), deposited Cu can be seen on the surface of the carbon fabric (Figure 1(b)). These particles are Cu from the anodic Cu plate during the EPD processing. Ionized Cu^{2+} are separated from the Cu plate and moves toward the cathodic carbon fabric under the electrical field. This phenomenon can be identified by observing the corroded surface of the Cu plate after cathodic electrophoresis. When the cathodic process was carried out by using PEI-treated CNTs dispersed in the suspension, both CNT and Cu were deposited at the same time and massive deposited particles were observed in Figure 1-(c). The composition of these particles was quantified by EDS: the normalized wt% of a carbon and a Cu was 84% and 16%, respectively. Although the results of normalized weight fraction are not absolutely confident due to the surface projection, the existence of Cu composition is notable.

Figure 1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of carbon fabric surfaces: (a) unmodified, Type 1; (b) Cu deposition by EPD, Type 2; (c) Cu/CNT deposition, Type 3; (d) Cu-coat by thermal evaporation, Type 4; (e) $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4+\text{HNO}_3$ oxidized CNT deposited on Cu-coated carbon fabric, Type 5; and (f) HNO_3 oxidized CNT deposited on Cu-coated carbon fabric, Type 6.

Figures 1(d)-(f) are the results of Cu coated carbon fabrics by thermal evaporation method. Prior to the EPD process, carbon fabric surface was coated with Cu as shown in

Fig. 1 (d). Cu-coated carbon fabrics which are deposited with acid-modified CNTs are shown in Figure 1-(e) and (f), respectively. In addition to uniform and high population of CNT deposition, numerous Cu platelets are observed on the carbon fiber surface. The platelets were found to be Cu elements from the EDX mapping results. During the migration of negatively charged CNTs, the thin layer of Cu on anodic carbon fiber surface was corroded in aqueous suspension due to the separation of Cu^{2+} from the layer.

Composites Characterization: Electrical Conductivity

Electrical conductivity was measured in both the in-plane and the out-of-plane directions. Figure 2 shows the results of electrical conductivities of multi-scale carbon/epoxy composites. It is noted that the in-plane electrical conductivity of carbon fabric composites was much higher than that in the through-the-thickness direction. This large difference is due to the fact that the in-plane property is dominated by the continuous carbon fibers, whereas, the out-of-plane property is dominated by the virtually non-conducting epoxy resin. Regardless of particle modifications, the in-plane electrical conductivities did not show significant changes. Nevertheless the electrical conductivities of modified carbon composites were improved by 20~40% compared with unmodified composites.

Figure 2. Electrical conductivity of Cu/CNT deposited carbon/epoxy composites: in-plane and through-the-thickness directions.

The through-the-thickness conductivity of copper coated carbon fabric composites was similar to that of unmodified composites because the resin layers between Cu coated fabrics play non-conducting barriers. When CNTs are deposited, the out-of-plane

electrical conductivity showed about one order of magnitude enhancement compared with unmodified composites. The electrical conductivities of PEI-treated and acid-modified CNTs on carbon fabrics were 2.969×10^{-2} S/cm and 5.45×10^{-3} S/cm, respectively. Whereas, the electrical conductivity of unmodified carbon fabric composites was 1.96×10^{-3} S/cm. The reason for higher improvement of electrical conductivity through the thickness is due to the fact that the nano-platelets of copper along with CNTs were effective in providing pathway for the electrical charge transfer in non-conducting matrix.

Composites Characterization: Mechanical Properties

The deposition of Cu without CNTs (Type 2) and Cu coated carbon fabric composites (Type 4) decreased the interlaminar shear strength by 6% and 14% compared with the unmodified carbon fabric composites due to the poor bonding between Cu and carbon fibers. The simultaneous deposition of CNTs and Cu (Type 3) increased the strength up to 10%. The ionized Cu particles are mixed with CNTs in particle base, which provided favorable role in crack deviation, and thus increased the interlaminar shear strength. The oxidized CNT deposition on Cu-coated carbon fabric composites (Type 5 and 6) was not effective in the improvement of strength. In this case, the Cu layer on the surface gave poor bonding with carbon fibers. Although CNTs are deposited, delaminations occur in the weak area between Cu and carbon fiber. This can be understood from the results of Type 4, in which Cu layers are coated on the carbon fibers directly. Oxidation using $H_2SO_4 + HNO_3$ might also damage the CNT surface, resulting in the poor bonding.

Figure 3. Interlaminar shear strength of Cu/CNT deposited carbon/epoxy composites.

After mechanical testing, specimens were fractured along the laminate direction. The SEM images in Figure 4 support the strength results. Figures 4 (b), (d) and (e) showed smooth surface of carbon fibers caused by brittle separation from the matrix. In Figure 4 (e), holes appearing between matrix and carbon fiber are the sites of pulled-out Cu

platelets. The Figure 4 (c) and (f), however, show that Cu and CNT were still on the carbon fibers and the matrix with good adhesion.

Figure 4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of carbon fabric surfaces: (a) unmodified, Type 1; (b) Cu deposition by EPD, Type 2; (c) Cu/CNT deposition, Type 3; (d) Cu-coat by thermal evaporation, Type 4; (e) $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4+\text{HNO}_3$ oxidized CNT deposited on Cu-coated carbon fabric, Type 5; and (f) HNO_3 oxidized CNT deposited on Cu-coated carbon fabric, Type 6.

SUMMARY

In this study, electrophoretic depositions have been applied to manufacturing of the multi-scale hybrid Cu-CNT carbon/epoxy composites. In addition to CNT reinforcement, Cu was also modified on carbon fabric using cathodic EPD and thermal evaporation method. Various deposition methods were examined by comparing the electrical conductivity and the interlaminar shear strength of the composites. SEM images and EDS analysis confirmed that Cu and CNTs deposition on carbon fabrics was relatively dense and uniform. In the case of simultaneous deposition of Cu and CNTs on carbon fabrics, electrical conductivity in the thickness direction increased one order of magnitude, and interlaminar shear strength improved by 10%, compared with unmodified carbon fabric composites. It can be conclude that Cu/CNTs deposition by the electrophoretic process allows the multifunctional properties of multi-scale hybrid composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was performed as a part of basic research program supported by Korea Institute of Materials Science (KIMS) and by the Korea Foundation for International Cooperation of Science & Technology(KICOS) through a grant provided by the Korean Ministry of Education, Science & Technology(MEST) in 2007 (No. K20704000090).

References

1. Erik T. Thostenson, Zhifeng Ren, Tsu-Wei Chou, *Composites Science and Technology* 61 (2001) 1899–1912.
2. Erik T. Thostenson, Tsu-Wei Chou, *Carbon* 44 (2006) 3022–3029.
3. E. T. Thostenson, W. Z. Li, D. Z. Wang, and Z. F. Ren, T. W. Chou, *Journal of Applied Physics* Vol.91-9 (2002).
4. R.B. Mathur, Sourav Chatterjee, B.P. Singh, *Composites Science and Technology* 68 (2008) 1608-1615.
5. L. Besra, M. Liu, *Progress in Materials Science* 52 (2007)1-61.
6. E. Bekyarova, E.T. Thostenson, A.Yu, H. Kim, J.Gao, J. Tang, N.T. Hahn, T-W. Chou, M.E. Itkis, R.C. Haddon, *Langmuir* 2007, 23, 3970-3974.
7. G. Zang, S. Sun, D. Yang, J. Dodelet, E. Sacher, *Carbon* 46(2008)196-205.